

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Gafforova N.A

BORROWINGS, FORMATION OF VOCABULARY AS LEXICAL DOUBLETS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/SENTABR

